

An Empirical Study on the Determinants of Financial Performance in Ethiopian Commercial Banks

Shikur Muhammed^{1*} Jaladi Ravi^{2*}

¹ *Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and Management Studies, Andhra University, Andhra Pradesh, India*

² *Research Director, Professor, Head Department of Commerce and Management Studies, Andhra University, Andhra Pradesh, India*

Abstract

This study investigates the bank-specific, industry-specific, and macroeconomic determinants of financial performance in Ethiopian commercial banks. It uses panel data from nine out of seventeen commercial banks operating in Ethiopia over the period 2008–2022. A quantitative research approach was employed using secondary data. Financial performance was measured using Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) as dependent variables. Based on the Hausman test, the random effects model was used for ROA and the fixed effects model for ROE. The explanatory variables include seven bank-specific factors (capital adequacy, operational efficiency, liquidity risk, income diversification, loan-to-deposit ratio, branch number, and credit risk), one industry-specific factor (size of the banking system), and two macroeconomic factors (real GDP growth rate and saving interest rate). The findings reveal that capital adequacy, operational efficiency, income diversification, loan-to-deposit ratio, branch number, credit risk, and size of the banking system significantly influence financial performance. Accordingly, bank management should focus on enhancing these key determinants to improve financial outcomes.

Keywords: Bank Specific Factors, Industry-Specific Factors, Financial Performance

1. Introduction

Financial institutions provide essential services that facilitate the flow of money within an economy, with banks serving as key financial intermediaries. Banks play a dynamic role by allocating financial resources, transferring funds from depositors to borrowers, and supporting investment activities. Beyond their intermediary function, the financial performance of banks significantly impacts a country's economic growth. Strong bank performance rewards investors, attracts further investment, and fosters economic development. Conversely, poor performance can lead to banking failures and economic instability. Therefore, understanding the determinants of bank financial performance is vital for assessing the stability of the financial sector and preventing potential crises. Globally, the banking sector serves as the backbone of modern trade and economic growth by acting as a primary source of finance (Ongore & Kusa, 2013).

Profitability is a critical concept for both financial and non-financial institutions, with commercial banks being key players within the financial sector. The success and sustainability of commercial banks largely depend on strategic initiatives, particularly in marketing and competitive positioning (Swarnapali, 2014). Beyond profitability, commercial banks also play a fundamental role in transmitting the central bank's monetary policy, thereby contributing significantly to the economic stability of a country (Siddiqui & Shoaib, 2011). Additionally, they facilitate trade and the payment system by reducing transaction costs and enhancing convenience.

In less monetized economies like Ethiopia, where the financial sector is predominantly composed of commercial banks, the effective and efficient performance of these institutions is vital for promoting economic growth. Today, the financial performance of banks is of great interest to a wide range of stakeholders—including customers, investors, governments, and the public—due to its direct implications for resource allocation and economic development (Raza et al., 2011). A stable and efficient banking sector forms the foundation for the financial performance of institutions, ultimately contributing to the achievement of broader economic objectives.

Numerous studies across the globe have explored the determinants of bank profitability, underscoring the growing significance of this topic. For example, Molyneux & Wilson (2004) analyzed the banking sectors of six European countries—Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the UK—over the period 1992–1998 using panel data and dynamic panel estimation methods. Their study identified key profitability determinants such as bank size, capital-asset ratio, credit risk, and ownership structure and found a strong relationship between bank-specific factors and profitability (measured by ROE). However, they found limited evidence linking industry-specific factors like ownership type to profitability outcomes.

In the context of Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), bank profitability is also shaped by a variety of internal and external factors. A study by McDonald (2009), which examined 389 banks across 41 SSA countries, found that bank-specific, industry-specific, and macroeconomic variables all had significant effects on profitability (measured by ROA). Their findings indicated that, on average, bank profits in SSA were higher than in other regions.

In Ethiopia, commercial banks are the cornerstone of the financial sector, playing a pivotal role in economic development by channeling funds from savers to investors. Their financial health is essential to the overall stability of the financial system. As such, understanding the factors that influence their profitability is critical to ensuring the sustainability and resilience of the banking industry. Given the dominant position of commercial banks in Ethiopia's financial sector, any disruption—such as insolvency or poor performance—could have a cascading effect on the broader economy, potentially triggering bank runs, systemic crises, and long-term economic setbacks.

Despite the importance of this subject, there remains a gap in the literature regarding the determinants of bank financial performance in the Ethiopian context. To address this gap, the current study investigates the impact of bank-specific, industry-specific, and macroeconomic factors on the financial performance of Ethiopian commercial banks during the period 2008 to 2022. Furthermore, recent banking failures and bailouts in developed economies have further underscored the need for a deeper understanding of what drives bank performance, making this research both timely and essential for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to safeguard Ethiopia's financial system.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical framework

In recent years, the soundness of the banking and financial system has gained increasing importance across countries. The financial sector—particularly the banking system—remains susceptible to systemic crises, prompting the establishment of costly safety nets such as deposit insurance schemes, which are often criticized for their associated moral hazard issues. Neely et al. (1997) argue that banks often operate as “black boxes” due to limited transparency and a general reluctance to disclose vital information. Assessing banks' creditworthiness and risk exposure is a complex task, as interpreting accounting data from financial institutions is not straightforward.

Kosmidou (2008) highlights that indicators such as business failures and non-performing loans (NPLs) are typically reported infrequently and, when available, may lack reliability due to banks' tendency to obscure problems for as long as possible. This underscores the need for comprehensive analysis using all available financial information from banks' official financial statements. Despite these limitations, traditional financial ratio analysis derived from financial statements remains a common tool employed by regulators to assess bank performance (Abdus, 2004).

A more structured examination of bank performance emerged in the late 1980s, incorporating theoretical models such as the Market Power (MP) and Efficiency Structure (ES) hypotheses (Athanasoglou & Delis, 2005). The MP hypothesis posits that profitability arises from external market conditions and that firms with substantial market share and a well-differentiated product portfolio can outperform competitors and earn monopolistic profits. In contrast, the ES hypothesis suggests that superior managerial and scale efficiencies lead to greater market concentration and, consequently, higher profitability. In addition, the Balanced Portfolio Theory, as by Olweny & Shiphoh (2011), offers another perspective by emphasizing that managerial decisions and overall policy directions directly shape a bank's profitability and returns to shareholders. Collectively, these theories suggest that both

internal and external factors influence bank performance.

2.2. Empirical studies

Sufian and Chong (2008) used return on assets (ROA) as the dependent variable to study the factors affecting the profitability of the Philippine banking industry from 1990 to 2005. All bank-specific factors appear to have a statistically significant effect on bank profitability, according to their empirical findings. In particular, non-interest income and capitalization have a positive impact on profitability, whereas size, credit risk, and overhead costs have a negative impact. While GDP growth, money supply growth, and stock market capitalization are found to be insignificant, only inflation has a significant negative impact among macroeconomic variables. With the dual goals of synthesising pertinent empirical literature and empirically testing profitability determinants for 28 commercial banks over the period 2003 to 2008 using a dynamic panel analysis, Ana et al. (2011) looked into the factors that affect bank profitability in Croatia. Profitability was represented by ROA. Their findings show that a stable depositor base, increased loan growth, equity financing, careful credit and market risk management, and the expansion of fee-based operations all contribute to increased bank profitability. On the other hand, interest expense and average interest income were not statistically significant.

Alper and Anbar (2011) examined the macroeconomic and bank-specific factors that affected Turkish commercial banks' profitability between 2002 and 2010. Their research, which used return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA) as dependent variables, showed that non-interest income and asset size significantly and favourably affected bank profitability. Azam and Siddiqui (2012) conducted a quarterly study using multiple regression analysis to examine the internal and external factors influencing bank profitability in Pakistan between 2004 and 2010. According to their findings, foreign banks were less impacted by macroeconomic factors in the host country and were typically more profitable than domestic ones. Foreign banks showed better capital efficiency, but local banks were more profitable in terms of earnings per share.

Using macroeconomic, industry-specific, and bank-specific factors, Ameer and Mhiri (2013) examined ten Tunisian commercial banks from 1998 to 2011. They discovered that capitalization and managerial effectiveness significantly and favourably affected bank performance using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). On the other hand, performance was adversely impacted by bank size and market concentration. The only macroeconomic factor that significantly (negatively) affected net interest margin was inflation, and privately held banks performed better than state-owned ones. Sanl and Heng (2013) investigated how the performance of commercial banks in China and Malaysia was impacted by bank-specific elements like size, operating costs, capital, credit, and liquidity. Return on average equity and return on average assets (ROAA) were used to gauge performance (ROAE). The findings indicate that these factors have different effects in the two nations, with operating ratios having a greater influence on Chinese banks than Malaysian ones. The effects of capital and credit ratios were comparable in both nations.

Ayanda et al. (2013) used co-integration and error correction techniques on annual data from 1980 to 2010 to investigate the factors that influence First Bank of Nigeria PLC's profitability. According to their findings, capital adequacy and credit risk had a negative short- and long-term impact on profitability, while bank size and cost effectiveness had no discernible effect. In the short term, liquidity risk had conflicting effects, and the only macroeconomic factor that had a positive impact on profitability was money supply growth. In order to determine the factors that influence bank performance in Kenya, Ongore and Gemechu (2013) used Generalized Least Squares (GLS) and linear multiple regression on panel data. The study discovered that while liquidity had little bearing on bank performance, capital adequacy, asset quality, and management effectiveness did. While asset quality had a negative impact, capital adequacy and management effectiveness had a positive one. Macroeconomic factors had an ambiguous impact, and ownership structure had no discernible impact.

Belayneh (2011) used balanced panel data to analyse the macroeconomic, industry-specific, and bank-specific factors that affected the profitability of seven Ethiopian commercial banks between 2001 and 2010. The dependent variable in the study was ROA. The results show that, with the exception of saving deposits, every bank-specific factor had a significant impact on profitability. Only economic growth demonstrated a significant correlation among macroeconomic variables, whereas market concentration was also significant. Habtamu (2012) used panel data from 2002 to 2011 to examine the

factors influencing the profitability of Ethiopia's private commercial banks. The study, which focused on ROA and ROE and used fixed effects regression, discovered that bank size, managerial effectiveness, and capital adequacy all had a significant impact on profitability. Furthermore, it was discovered that regulatory factors and GDP growth had significant effects.

Tekeste (2012) investigated Ethiopian commercial banks' profitability factors from 1999/2000 to 2008/2009. The equity-to-asset ratio, non-interest income, and bank size all had a positive and significant impact on profitability, according to the study, which used ROAA as the profitability indicator. Although they had a negative impact on profitability, loan loss reserves were not statistically significant. Macroeconomic variables like GDP and inflation were deemed to be negligible, and liquidity and operational effectiveness suffered. Between 2001 and 2008, Abebaw (2012) compared the ownership structure and performance of Ethiopian commercial banks. According to the findings, private banks performed better than public banks in terms of return on assets (ROA) and net interest margin (NIM), indicating that they are more adept at using their assets efficiently and making money off of interest-bearing investments.

Dawit (2016) examined the financial performance of seven private commercial banks in Ethiopia from 2000 to 2014. Multiple regression models were used in the study to analyse ROA, ROE, and NIM. The findings demonstrated that financial performance was significantly influenced by bank size, earning capacity, capital adequacy, asset quality, and liquidity management. Foreign exchange rates and regulatory concerns were also important macroeconomic factors. The industry's growth and expansion—exemplified by the number of commercial bank branches, the expanding branch network that serves remote areas, the total assets and capital, and the growing size of the banking system—further emphasises the necessity of looking into the factors influencing financial performance in the Ethiopian banking sector. These elements are all in line with the industry's steady profitability.

3. Method, Data, and Analysis

An explanatory research design was employed to evaluate the factors of financial performance in commercial banks in Ethiopia, aiming to explore cause-and-effect correlations. A quantitative research methodology was utilized, drawing on secondary data sourced from the audited financial statements of the chosen commercial banks and the annual reports of the National Bank of Ethiopia. The data were analyzed via STATA version 16 software.

3.1. Sampling and Data Collection

The target population for this study includes all commercial banks registered with the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) and currently operating in the country. The country presently has one state-owned bank and twenty-six private commercial banks in operation. Kothari (2004) emphasised that a well-designed sample must be feasible, taking into account the time and financial resources available for the research. This study selected commercial banks in Ethiopia that have been operational for a minimum of fifteen years and possess audited financial statements, utilising a non-probability (judgemental) sampling technique. This study examined the following banks: Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, Awash Bank, Dashen Bank, Bank of Abyssinia, Wegagen Bank, United Bank, Nib International Bank, Cooperative Bank of Oromia, and Lion International Bank.

The research utilised secondary data sources. The study utilised data from the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE), the Ministry of Finance and Economic Development (MOFED), and the annual audited financial statements, including the balance sheet and income statement, of selected commercial banks. This research employed both descriptive and inferential statistics utilising panel data. A descriptive analysis delineates behavioural patterns or pertinent aspects of phenomena, providing detailed information regarding each variable. Consequently, the mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviations of each variable were utilised. The collected data was processed and analysed using STATA version 17 software packages. Consequently, regression results will be displayed in a tabular format, including the relevant test statistics.

3.2. Model Specification

The nature of the data used in this study enables the researcher to use the panel regression model. The general formula used for this model is:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 IndS_{it} + \beta_3 Macro_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1).$$

Where Y_{it} denotes the performance indicator, represented by ROA and ROE; BS_{it} is a vector of bank-specific variables; $IndS_{it}$ represents industry-specific variables, and $Macro_{it}$ includes macroeconomic variables that are assumed to influence performance. α_i captures unobserved time-invariant effects specific to banks, industries, and macro conditions, while ϵ_{it} is the error term.

Then, the equation for ROA and ROE as the dependent variable were:

$$ROA_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CAR_{i,t} + \beta_2 CIR_{i,t} + \beta_3 LIQ_{i,t} + \beta_4 DIV_{i,t} + \beta_5 LDR_{i,t} + \beta_6 CRR_{i,t} + \beta_7 BRN_{i,t} + \beta_8 SBS_t + \beta_9 GDP_t + \beta_{10} SIR_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$ROE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CAR_{i,t} + \beta_2 CIR_{i,t} + \beta_3 LIQ_{i,t} + \beta_4 DIV_{i,t} + \beta_5 LDR_{i,t} + \beta_6 CRR_{i,t} + \beta_7 BRN_{i,t} + \beta_8 SBS_t + \beta_9 GDP_t + \beta_{10} SIR_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

The model incorporates several variables to measure the performance of commercial banks. The dependent variables are ROA_{it} (Return on Average Asset) and ROE_{it} (Return on Average Equity), which represent the financial performance of bank i at time t . The bank-specific factors include CAR_{it} (Capital strength), CIR_{it} (Cost to income ratio, representing operational efficiency), DIV_{it} (Income diversification), LIQ_{it} (Liquidity risk), LDR_{it} (Loan Deposit Ratio), CRR_{it} (Credit risk ratio), and BRN_{it} (Branch number). Industry-specific variables include SBS_t (Size of the bank system), while macroeconomic factors are represented by GDP_t (Real GDP growth) and SIR_t (Saving interest rate). The error term is denoted by $\epsilon_{i,t}$, capturing unobserved factors affecting the financial performance of the banks.

3.3. Description of variables

The following Table presents the definitions, measurements, and sources for the variables used in the study to analyze the financial performance of commercial banks. Each variable is designed to capture specific aspects of bank performance, ranging from profitability (ROA, ROE) to risk and operational efficiency. The data used for these variables are sourced from various studies, providing a comprehensive foundation for understanding the determinants of bank performance in the Ethiopian banking sector. The variables cover both internal factors (such as capital adequacy, credit risk, and income diversification) and external macroeconomic variables (such as GDP growth and saving interest rates).

Table 1. Summary of Potential factors that influence the level of NPLs, corresponding measures, and hypothetic effects on non-performing loans.

Variable	Notation	Measurement	source
Return on Asset	ROA	NIBT /Total asset	Chan & Vong, (2008)
Return on Equity	ROE	NIBT / Total Equity	Gemechu,B, (2013)
Capital Adequacy	CAR	Total Capital/Total Asset	Ezra, (2013)
Operational Efficiency	CIR	Noninterest expense / Total income	Wanzenriedb, (2009)
Liquidly risk	LRQ	Current Asset / Total deposit	(Hadad,2013)
Income Diversification	DIV	Noninterest income / Total asset	(Rasiah, 2010)
Loan-to-deposit ratio	LDR	Total loan / Total Deposit	Sofoklis (2009)
Credit Risk	CRR	Loan Loss Provision / Total Loan	Podder (2012),
Branch number	BRN	Branch number of sample banks	Ongore & kusa, (2013)
Size Bank system	SBS	The total asset of all banks to GDP	Huizingha, (1999)

Source: Table by authors

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents a summary of descriptive statistics, providing general descriptions of both dependent and independent variables in the data. The total number of observations for each variable is 135, representing data from nine banks spanning the years 2008 to 2022. The mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values of each variable were utilised to illustrate the overall trend of the data during the specified period.

Table 2. Summary of descriptive statistics for dependent and independent variable

Variables	N	Mean	Std. dev	Minimum	Maximum
ROA	135	0.0361239	0.0102301	0.0034569	0.0647385
ROE	135	0.3362388	0.1917362	0.0194964	1.0449470
CAR	135	0.1247035	0.0414059	0.0418656	0.2013324
CIR	135	0.3452695	0.1071291	0.0897945	0.7534752
LRQ	135	1.2878310	0.1239204	0.9375891	1.7787890
DIV	135	0.0332318	0.0112616	0.0090591	0.0625315
LDR	135	0.5892983	0.1092722	0.2228420	0.8911559
CRR	135	0.0077481	0.0162125	0.0000000	0.1089827
BRN	135	190.0889	250.42900	16	1280
SBS	135	0.0515331	0.1023731	0.0025137	0.5147711
GDP	135	9.7870000	1.1847860	7.7	11.4
SIR	135	5	0.7789362	4	7

Source: Table by authors

The descriptive statistics reveal important insights into the financial performance and determinants among the sampled commercial banks in Ethiopia. The Return on Assets (ROA), which measures how efficiently a bank uses its assets to generate net income before tax (NIBT), had an average value of 3.61 percent. This suggests that, on average, the banks earned 3.61 cents for every birr of assets. The highest and lowest ROA values were 6.47 percent and 0.35 percent, respectively, indicating significant variation in profitability across banks. Similarly, the Return on Equity (ROE), which indicates how much profit banks generated from shareholders' equity, averaged 33.62 percent. This shows that, on average, the sampled banks earned 33.62 cents for every birr of equity invested, reflecting strong financial performance when compared to ROA.

Among the explanatory variables, capital adequacy—measured as the ratio of total equity to total assets—had a mean of 12.47 percent, with values ranging from 4.19 to 20.13 percent and a standard deviation of 4.14 percent. Operational efficiency, proxied by the cost-to-income ratio, averaged 34.53 percent, with a wide spread between the minimum (8.98 percent) and maximum (75.35 percent), indicating differences in cost management among banks. Liquidity risk, calculated as liquid assets over total deposits, had a high average of 128.78 percent, ranging from 93.76 to 177.88 percent, with a standard deviation of 12.39 percent. Income diversification, captured by the ratio of non-interest income to total assets, had an average of 3.32 percent, with values spanning from 0.91 to 6.25 percent.

The loan-to-deposit ratio, reflecting the extent of banks' lending activity relative to their deposits, averaged 58.93 percent, ranging from 22.28 to 89.11 percent. Credit risk, measured by the loan loss provision to total loans, was relatively low, with a mean of 0.77 percent and a maximum value of 10.90

percent. The number of bank branches had a wide variation, with an average of 190.09 branches and a range from 16 to 1,280, indicating differences in outreach among the banks. The size of the banking system, defined as the ratio of total banking assets to GDP, had a mean of 5.15 percent. Real GDP growth averaged 9.79 percent during the study period, ranging from 7.7 to 11.4 percent. Lastly, the saving interest rate showed moderate variation, with an average of 5 percent and a range from 4 to 7 percent. These statistics highlight the diversity and financial dynamics within Ethiopia's commercial banking sector during the study period.

4.2. Choosing Random Effect Vs Fixed Effect Model

The Hausman test determined the study's fixed or random-effects model appropriateness. The Hausman specification test showed ROA model P-values of 1.0000, which above the 5% level of significance. Thus, the random effect model null hypothesis is valid. However, Hausman specification tests showed ROE model P-values of 0.0015, below 5% significance. Thus, at 5% significance, the fixed effect model null hypothesis is valid.

4.3. Test for Classical Linear Regression Model Assumptions

As noted by Brooks (2008), when the key assumptions hold true, it ensures that the model incorporates all relevant data. However, violations of these assumptions suggest that some information might be excluded from the model. Therefore, prior to assessing the significance of the slopes and interpreting the regression results, it is crucial to conduct tests for stationarity, normality, multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heteroskedasticity. These tests help detect any potential data issues and ensure the model's fitness and the overall quality of the research.

To assess the validity of the regression model assumptions, several diagnostic tests were conducted. First, the Jarque-Bera test was applied to examine the normality of residuals. The results indicated no evidence of non-normality, as both skewness and kurtosis values fell within the acceptable range of -1.0 to $+1.0$. This confirms that the residuals were normally distributed for both ROA and ROE models. Next, multicollinearity among the independent variables was tested using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The average VIF was 3.25, which is well below the commonly accepted threshold of 10, indicating that multicollinearity was not a concern in the analysis.

To detect the presence of heteroskedasticity, the Breusch-Pagan test was employed. The results showed that the p-values for both ROA and ROE models were greater than 0.05, implying that the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity could not be rejected. Hence, there was no evidence of heteroskedasticity in the data. Furthermore, to test for autocorrelation, the Breusch-Godfrey LM test was conducted. The test results confirmed the absence of autocorrelation, with p-values of 0.6817 for the ROA model and 0.3775 for the ROE model. Overall, the diagnostic tests verified that the regression models met the key assumptions required for reliable estimation and inference.

4.4. Results and Discussions

This section outlines the regression results obtained from both Random Effects and Fixed Effects models, utilised to analyse the factors influencing financial performance among commercial banks in Ethiopia. The analysis was performed utilising STATA 17 software. According to the model selection criteria outlined previously, the Random Effects model was considered suitable for the analysis of Return on Assets (ROA), whereas the Fixed Effects model was chosen for the analysis of Return on Equity (ROE).

Table 4. Results of the Random effect model regressed using ROA as a proxy of financial performance

Random-effects GLS regression						
R-squared: within = 0.8622				N = 135		
Adjusted R-squared = 0.8607				Number of groups= 9		
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)				Obs per group: =15		
				Wald chi2 (10) = 488.31		
				Prob> chi2 = 0.0000		
ROA	Coefficient	Std. Err	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
CAR	0.0326772	0.0145252	2.25	0.024	0.0042084	0.0611461
CIR	-0.0473072	0.0055569	-8.51	0.000	-0.0581985	-0.0364159
LRQ	0.0003847	0.0041555	0.09	0.926	-0.0077599	0.0085292
DIV	0.6750487	0.0514298	13.13	0.000	0.5742482	0.7758492
LDR	0.0134095	0.0056027	2.39	0.017	0.0024285	0.0243905
CRR	-0.1999763	0.0307828	-6.50	0.000	-0.2603094	-0.1396432
BRN	-0.0000129	5.06e-06	-2.55	0.011	-0.0000228	2.97e-06
SBS	0.0657068	0.0128219	5.12	0.000	0.0405763	0.090847
GDP	0.0004515	0.0004495	1.00	0.315	-0.0004296	0.001333
SIR	0.0014463	0.0008579	1.69	0.092	-0.0002352	0.00313
_cons	0.0065138	0.0101141	0.64	0.520	0.013309	0.026337
sigma_u=	0					
sigma_e=	0.00347933					
rho=	0 (fraction of variance due to u_i)					

Source: Table by authors

The results of the estimation presented in Table 4 show that the R-squared value is 0.8622, while the adjusted R-squared value stands at 0.8607. The data indicates that the model demonstrates significant explanatory capability, accounting for more than 86% of the variation in Return on Assets (ROA) among Ethiopian commercial banks, as elucidated by the independent variables incorporated in the model. The remaining 14% of the variation in ROA can be attributed to factors that are not included in the model.

The intercept coefficient (α) is 0.0065138, which is statistically significant at the 5% level. This implies that when all explanatory variables are held at zero, the average ROA would be approximately 0.0065. Furthermore, the probability value ($p = 0.000$) for the overall model indicates that the model is highly significant at the 1% level, and that the explanatory variables jointly influence the ROA of Ethiopian commercial banks.

The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), defined as the ratio of total capital to total assets, is 0.0326772, with a p-value of 0.024. Holding other variables constant, a 1% increase in CAR correlates with a 3.27% increase in ROA, which is statistically significant at the 5% level. The null hypothesis positing that CAR does not influence ROA is rejected. The anticipated positive relationship can be explained by the capacity of well-capitalized banks to absorb losses and capitalise on profitable opportunities, resulting in

enhanced performance. This finding is consistent with earlier research (Athanasoglou et al., 2005; Flamini et al., 2009; Naceur & Goaid; Belayneh, 2011), which emphasises the significance of capital adequacy in influencing profitability.

The coefficient for Cost to Income Ratio (CIR), a proxy for operational efficiency, is -0.0473072; p-value 0.000. Statistically significant at the 1% level, this suggests that a 1% rise in CIR results in a 4.73% decline in ROA. Higher operational expenses lower profitability, hence this negative correlation was anticipated. The outcome is in line with Athanasoglou et al. (2005) and Dietrich & Wanzenried (2009), who claim that poor cost structures compromise banks' performance. Ethiopian banks therefore have to increase operational efficiency in order to be profitable.

The coefficient for Liquidity Risk (LRQ), measured by current assets to current liabilities, is 0.0003847, with a p-value of 0.926. This relationship is statistically insignificant, suggesting that LRQ has no significant impact on ROA. Although a positive relationship was observed, it lacks statistical support. The insignificant result could stem from the practice of Ethiopian banks holding substantial deposits without aggressively converting them into loans. This contradicts prior findings (Yuqi, 2006; Tobias & Themba, 2011) that highlight liquidity as a critical factor in bank performance and failure.

The coefficient for Income Diversification (DIV), measured by non-interest income to total assets, is 0.6750487, with a p-value of 0.000. A 1% increase in DIV leads to a 67.5% increase in ROA, statistically significant at the 1% level. This positive and significant relationship suggests that Ethiopian banks benefit from diversifying their income streams beyond traditional interest income. The result aligns with Rasiah (2010), reinforcing the idea that non-interest income is a key driver of profitability. Banks are encouraged to enhance income diversification to improve performance.

The coefficient for Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) is 0.0134095, with a p-value of 0.017, indicating statistical significance at the 5% level. A 1% increase in LDR is associated with a 1.34% increase in ROA. This positive relationship suggests that banks extending more loans relative to deposits tend to be more profitable. This finding supports the results of Alexiou & Sofoklis (2009) and Ana et al. (2011). It implies that Ethiopian banks should mobilize deposits and expand lending to enhance performance.

The coefficient for Credit Risk Ratio (CRR), measured by loan loss provision to total loans, is -0.1999763, with a p-value of 0.000. A 1% increase in CRR leads to a 20% decrease in ROA, statistically significant at the 1% level. This negative and significant relationship was expected, as higher credit risk (more provisions for bad loans) diminishes profitability. The result agrees with Podder (2012), who identified credit risk as a major contributor to bank failure. Thus, Ethiopian banks must enhance credit risk management and improve loan recovery processes.

The coefficient for Branch Number (BRN) is -0.000129, with a p-value of 0.011, indicating statistical significance at the 5% level. This suggests that an increase in the number of branches by one unit leads to a 0.013% decrease in ROA. Contrary to expectations, the effect is negative, possibly due to banks expanding branch networks without adequately assessing the economic viability of the locations. Branch proliferation without strategic planning may dilute profits. Banks are advised to conduct feasibility studies before opening new branches to ensure financial efficiency.

The coefficient for the Size of Banking System (SBS), measured by total assets to real GDP, is 0.0657068, with a p-value of 0.000. A 1% increase in SBS results in a 6.57% increase in ROA, which is statistically significant at the 1% level. This positive and significant relationship indicates that larger banking systems in Ethiopia are associated with better performance. Larger banks benefit from economies of scale and market dominance, resulting in higher profit margins. The finding confirms the hypothesis that banking system size positively affects profitability.

Table 5. Results of the Fixed effect model regressed using ROE as a proxy of financial performance

Fixed-effects (within) regression						
R-squared: within = 0.8900						
Adjusted R-squared = 0.9104						
		Number of obs. = 135 Number of groups = 9 Obs per group = 15 F (10, 71) = 57.42 Prob > F = 0.0000				
ROE	Coefficient	Std. Err	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
CAR	-2.7415270	0.2890115	-9.49	0.000	-3.3178000	-2.1652550
CIR	-0.4745774	0.0838607	-5.66	0.000	-0.6417909	-0.3073640
LRQ	0.1716750	0.0751105	2.29	0.025	0.0219089	0.3214410
DIV	3.0965310	0.8909062	3.48	0.001	1.3201150	4.8729480
LDR	0.3817013	0.0765299	4.99	0.000	0.2291050	0.5342975
CRR	-1.5906800	0.4516338	-3.52	0.001	-2.4912130	-0.6901481
BRN	-0.0004367	0.0000676	-6.46	0.000	-0.0005716	-0.0003019
SBS	2.2166770	0.2287824	9.69	0.000	1.7604980	2.6728570
GDP	0.0076088	0.0056252	1.35	0.180	-0.0036076	0.0188251
SIR	0.0190003	0.0110674	1.72	0.090	-0.0030675	0.0410681
_cons	0.1046864	0.1523526	0.69	0.494	-0.1990961	0.4084689
sigma_e	0 .05031891					
rho	0.56639812 (fraction of variance due to u_i)					

Source: Table by authors

The estimation results outlined in Table 5 indicate that the R-squared and adjusted R-squared values are 0.8900 and 0.9104, respectively, suggesting a robust model fit. Approximately 89% of the variation in Return on Equity (ROE) of Ethiopian commercial banks can be attributed to the independent variables included in the model. Eleven percent of the variation can be accounted for by additional factors that are not included in the regression analysis.

The intercept coefficient (α) is 0.1046864, indicating that when all explanatory factors are set to zero, the average ROE would be 10.47%. This value is statistically insignificant at the 5% significance level. The F-statistic p-value is 0.000, signifying that the total model is statistically significant at the 1% level and that the independent variables collectively exert a substantial influence on ROE.

The coefficient of Capital Adequacy Ratio is -2.741527, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a statistically significant negative effect on ROE at the 1% level. This suggests that a 1% increase in CAR leads to a 27.42% decrease in ROE, holding other factors constant. The finding contradicts the expected positive relationship and prior studies (Athanasoglou et al., 2005; Flamini et al., 2009; Naceur & Goaid; Belayneh, 2011). A possible explanation is that a higher capital base reduces the income generated per unit of shareholder equity, as Ethiopian banks tend to rely more on customer deposits than on shareholder capital.

The Cost-to-Income Ratio coefficient is -0.04745774 with a p-value of 0.000 , indicating a statistically significant negative relationship between operational efficiency and ROE at the 1% level. A 1% increase in CIR results in a 4.75% decrease in ROE. This outcome aligns with expectations and earlier studies (Athanasoglou et al., 2005; Dietrich & Wanzenried, 2009), where higher non-interest expenses negatively affect bank profitability.

The coefficient of Liquidity Risk (LRQ) is 0.171675 , with a p-value of 0.025 , showing a positive and statistically significant impact on ROE at the 5% level. A 1% increase in LRQ leads to a 2.52% increase in ROE, holding other variables constant. This finding is contrary to prior research (Yuqi, 2006; Tobias & Themba, 2011), which found liquidity issues to be major contributors to bank failures. However, in the Ethiopian context, it may reflect prudent liquidity management practices and conservative asset allocation strategies.

The coefficient for income diversification (DIV) is 3.096531 , with a p-value of 0.001 , suggesting a positive and significant effect on ROE at the 1% level. A 1% increase in DIV is associated with a 309.65% increase in ROE. The result aligns with expectations, as banks that generate more income from non-interest sources tend to experience improved profitability. This underscores the importance of diversifying income streams in enhancing bank performance in Ethiopia.

The Loan-to-Deposit Ratio coefficient is 0.3817013 , with a p-value of 0.000 , indicating a statistically significant positive relationship with ROE at the 1% level. A 1% increase in LDR increases ROE by 38.17%. This is consistent with studies by Alexiou & Sofoklis (2009) and Ana et al. (2011), which found that higher loan disbursement boosts profitability. The result suggests that increased lending contributes positively to the financial performance of Ethiopian banks.

The Credit Risk Ratio coefficient is -1.59068 , with a p-value of 0.001 , showing a strong negative effect on ROE at the 1% level. A 1% increase in CRR results in a 159.07% decrease in ROE, confirming the expected outcome. This implies that higher provisions for loan losses significantly impair profitability. The result is consistent with Podder (2012), highlighting the negative impact of credit risk on bank performance.

The branch number (BRN) coefficient is -0.0004367 , with a p-value of 0.000 , indicating a statistically significant negative relationship with ROE at the 1% level. An increase of one branch results in a 0.04% decline in ROE. Though a positive relationship was hypothesized, the negative result might reflect the high operational costs of underutilized or poorly performing branches. It also suggests the need for a more strategic branch expansion plan.

The coefficient for Size of the Banking System is 2.216677 , with a p-value of 0.000 , indicating a strong positive and significant impact on ROE at the 1% level. A 1% increase in SBS leads to a 221.67% increase in ROE. This aligns with the expected outcome that larger banking systems enjoy economies of scale and generate higher profits. However, contrasting studies (Demirgüç-Kunt & Huizinga, 1999; Dermine & Schoemaker, 2010) argue that larger banks may take on riskier assets, potentially reducing profitability.

5. Conclusions and Suggestions

5.1. Conclusion

Based on the regression results presented above, the study identifies the key internal and external determinants of the financial performance of Ethiopian commercial banks, measured by Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

For ROA, the analysis shows that Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Income Diversification (DIV), Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR), and Size of the Banking System (SBS) have a positive and statistically significant effect. This implies that improvements in these variables—such as better capital positioning, diversified income sources, higher lending efficiency, and a more robust banking sector—contribute positively to the banks' financial performance. Conversely, Cost to Income Ratio (CIR), Credit Risk (CRR), and Branch Network (BRN) exhibit a negative and significant relationship with ROA, indicating that higher operational inefficiencies, increased credit risk, and excessive expansion in

branch networks can adversely affect profitability. In contrast, Liquidity Risk (LRQ), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and Savings Interest Rate (SIR) were found to have no statistically significant effect on ROA, suggesting that these macroeconomic variables do not directly influence the return on assets of commercial banks in the Ethiopian context during the study period.

Regarding ROE, the results indicate that Liquidity Risk (LRQ), Income Diversification (DIV), Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR), and Size of the Banking System (SBS) have a positive and significant impact, highlighting their contribution to enhancing shareholders' returns. On the other hand, Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Cost to Income Ratio (CIR), Credit Risk (CRR), and Branch Network (BRN) show a negative and significant effect on ROE, implying that higher capital buffers, inefficient cost structures, increased credit risk, and excessive branch expansion reduce returns to equity holders. Similar to the findings for ROA, GDP and SIR were found to be insignificant in explaining changes in ROE, underscoring the relatively limited role of these macroeconomic factors in determining bank performance in terms of equity returns.

Overall, the study concludes that internal bank-specific factors—particularly capital adequacy, cost efficiency, credit risk, income diversification, and lending practices—are the most influential determinants of financial performance for Ethiopian commercial banks. While selected macroeconomic variables like GDP and SIR were considered, their impact was found to be insignificant. Therefore, bank management and policymakers should focus more on optimizing internal operational and financial strategies to enhance both ROA and ROE, thereby strengthening the overall performance and resilience of the banking sector.

5.2. Suggestions

The study's findings indicate that the financial performance of Ethiopian commercial banks, as assessed through Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE), is primarily affected by factors specific to the banks themselves. The factors encompass capital adequacy, operational efficiency, liquidity risk, income diversification, loan-to-deposit ratio, credit risk, and the number of branches. Given that these factors are primarily managed by bank leadership, there is potential to improve financial performance through targeted strategies and efficient oversight of these elements.

To this end, the management bodies of Ethiopian commercial banks are advised to strengthen these key internal factors. Enhancing capital adequacy, for instance, can be achieved by selling shares to both existing shareholders and potential new investors entering the banking industry. Improving operational efficiency—particularly through cost minimization—can also significantly contribute to profitability. This includes managing non-interest expenses such as administrative costs. For example, collaboration in installing shared ATM infrastructure could reduce overhead costs and improve service efficiency.

Moreover, income diversification has emerged as a critical component in driving bank profitability. Therefore, banks should actively pursue non-interest income sources, such as fees from ATM services, foreign transactions (like money transfers and letters of credit), and other financial services. Such diversification is especially important in mitigating risks associated with loan defaults and interest rate fluctuations. Additionally, increasing deposit mobilization remains a fundamental goal. A higher deposit base enables banks to disburse more loans, earn greater interest income, and build capital reserves through retained earnings rather than relying solely on dividend distributions. This, in turn, boosts total assets and strengthens financial performance.

The study also highlights the importance of branch expansion as a means to collect more resources and improve the overall size and reach of banks. A well-distributed branch network not only contributes to resource mobilization but also enhances the visibility and competitiveness of banks. Furthermore, investing in physical infrastructure and acquiring fixed assets can contribute positively to long-term performance and stability. Finally, while this study provides a comprehensive analysis of the internal determinants of bank performance in Ethiopia, it acknowledges that the variables considered are not exhaustive. Therefore, future research is encouraged to explore additional bank-specific and macroeconomic factors—particularly regulatory variables—that may further explain variations in financial performance across banks.

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